

Ocean Modelling of Scottish Coastal Waters

Through this Story Map you can learn about ocean modelling, particularly within Scottish coastal seas.

1. Motivation and Context

We value the ocean. In Scotland, we benefit from a coastal sea, a rich marine biodiversity, many resources, a very long coastline and many islands. "Valuing the ocean" can vary from enjoying solitude on a beach in winter to building wealth from offshore resources. All values must be safeguarded against external threats and competing values.

Decisions must be made and should be based on values and knowledge. Experts have a role in predicting the effects of decisions.

In this storyboard, we describe how one group of experts based in Scotland can provide some of the expertise and help inform decisions. To view some examples of models in use, see the [Case Studies](#) section.

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Who are we?

We are all members of MASTS, a consortium of organisations engaged in marine science that represents the majority of Scotland's marine research capacity. More specifically, we are the “modellers” within MASTS, who use various types of marine models (simplified representations of the ocean) as a primary tool in our work. Each of us use other methods also, but we value models and use this space to explain why, and to describe what we do and how it can be used.

We want to help make wise decisions. But why should models that are an incomplete and simplified representation of reality be useful?

Why Model?

To Understand

- The coastal ocean is complicated
- We may be puzzled what is going on...
- ... but we may have an idea or two and by representing the coastal ocean with a model, we can test those ideas

To Interpolate and Infer

Some properties can be observed, but not all the time, and other properties may be immeasurable. We can use a model to interpolate across space and time and infer the immeasurable.

In the example to the left, the left hand image shows cloud-affected mapping of chlorophyll based on satellite measurements. There are gaps caused by clouds. To address this, other data and a model are used to fill the 'missing space', to form the complete (but inexact) image on the right.

To Predict and Project

- We can **predict** how the coastal ocean will change.
- We can **project** the effect of proposed developments or external change (e.g. global heating).
- The ability to project is necessary to **advise**.

As an example, projections of changing sea temperatures around Scotland are essential. The image on the left shows 'projected annual mean sea surface temperature change between 2000-2019 and 2079-2098'.

For Whom?

Who do we work with?

- Other Scientists
 - Observers - models need to represent reality!
 - Other hydrodynamic modellers - intercomparison helps us all improve
 - Allied models - coupling other models, and providing input to other models, broadens the use of our models
- Professionals
 - Executives and engineers in commercial companies
 - Government and environmental agencies
 - Third sector
- Public
 - Encourage interest in the marine environment at all ages
 - Provide sound information to inform views

Example: the volume V of a rectangular box defined by length L , width W , and height H : $V = L \times W \times H$

Mathematical Models

Analytical Models

Studies of regional coastal waters typically rely on mathematical models. In some cases, a simplified representation of the system allows for an analytical solution, meaning the state of the system can be expressed directly with a mathematical formula without the need for iterative computation and complex algorithms.

Numerical Models

However, coastal systems are often too complex to be represented analytically. In such cases, numerical models are required. These models solve the governing equations by dividing space and time into discrete elements, providing an idealised but practical representation of real coastal environments.

The following sections introduce the key components used to construct a hydrodynamic model for coastal systems.

Numerical Models: Spatial discretisation

The simplest approach to spatially discretising a domain is to use a structured grid composed of rectangular cells. A more flexible, though computationally more complex, alternative is to use an unstructured grid, where the domain is discretised into triangular or other irregularly shaped cells. This approach allows the grid to more accurately represent complex coastlines and irregular geometries.

Numerical Models: Time discretisation

Estimation of the progress of the state of the system to a later time, is calculated from the previous state, the timestep and the governing equations. The time-stepping method discretise the system's evolution in time slices, and in a similar way the volume of water is divided into increments of depth, latitude and longitude to allow spatial resolution of the system. At each timestep, and each spatial cell, the system's equations are solved.

Structured Grid

Structured Grid

Numerical Models: Water properties throughout the discretised domain

Water properties such as temperature and salinity are defined within each grid cell, while velocity components describe the corresponding transports between adjacent cells. The illustration provides an example in the case of a structured grid.

3. Case studies

Case Study 1. Forecasting spread of Harmful Algal Blooms

Harmful algal blooms (HABs) can have serious impacts on the marine environment. They can be toxic to both humans and marine life, with the potential to kill fish and other marine organisms. However, models can be used to predict their occurrence and spread, allowing us to mitigate some of their impacts.

Around the Scottish coastline, forecasting the risk of HABs is particularly valuable for the aquaculture industry. The complex coastline and bathymetry is challenging to model, with many aquaculture sites situated in sheltered bays and coastal regions. The WeStCOMS model was developed specifically for this area, using an unstructured mesh that allows the model to resolve small-scale features by focussing resolution in key areas. This model now provides 5-day forecasts of circulation around the

west coast of Scotland, supporting predictions of HABs spread (and other materials) in the ocean. Up to date reports on HABs risk around Scotland can now be found here: habreports.org

Similar approaches are also being developed to predict the risk of sea lice outbreaks, as discussed in [Case Study 2](#).

If you would like to make use of WeStCOMS, data from the ocean forecasts, can be found here: <https://thredds.sams.ac.uk/thredds/catalog/SCOATS.html>

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More information about the methods used to develop the forecasts can also be found in [Aleynik et al. \(2016\)](#) and [Davidson et al. \(2021\)](#).

Case Study 2: Predicting the spread of sea lice

Sea lice are tiny copepods that spend some of their life cycle attached to wild fish as parasites. Sea lice regularly infect farmed salmon and the fish farming industry have to continuously monitor and treat their farmed fish for sea lice. It is important to

also monitor (for a successful [Blue Economy](#)) and model the wider marine environment to understand the potential risks posed by sea lice originating from salmon farms in Scotland to wild and farmed salmonids.

The Salmon Parasite in Linnhe, Lorn and Shuna (SPILLS) project focused on testing and improving sea lice dispersal monitoring and modelling techniques and compared different models designed to predict the distribution of sea lice in Scottish sea lochs (focusing on the sea lochs of Linnhe, Lorn and Shuna). Comparing and combining model outputs can help us understand more about model performance, allowing us to provide improved advice on how results should be interpreted.

The animation in the video shows modelled dispersion of sea lice larvae from one of the models used in this study. It shows the spread in the near-surface layer (2 m deep), from 8 active salmon farms in Shuna Sound, Argyll, west Scotland. The simulation was produced using outputs from the UnPTRACK lice dispersal model ([Gillibrand et al., 2023](#)), using flow fields from the WestCOMS hydrodynamic model ([Aleynik et al., 2016](#)).

The SPILLS project was funded by the Scottish Government Marine Directorate and Crown Estate Scotland as part of its enabling role to invest in research and development to enhance sustainability and explore new areas of potential growth of the aquaculture sector. The project involved collaboration between farm operators (Mowi Scotland Ltd., Kames Fish Farming Ltd.), a number of local fisheries trusts and organizations (Argyll Fisheries Trust, Argyll District Salmon Fishery Board, Fisheries Management Scotland), The Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS) and the Scottish Government Marine Directorate. For more information on outcomes from this project, the full report can be found on the [Scottish Government website](#).

Case Study 3: Hindcasting drift path of WWI shipwreck casualties

The HMS Stephen Furness was sunk by German U-boats on the afternoon of 13 December 1917 in the Irish Sea, between the Northern Ireland and the Isle of Man. In the month that followed, several casualties were washed ashore near Anglesey on the Welsh coast, approximately 150 km away from the site of the sinking, where they were buried.

This study investigated how complex marine processes could have transported the bodies over this distance within a month's timeframe. Historical sea conditions were reconstructed by combining tidal data with archived wind records from the UK Met Office within a hydrodynamic model. A particle tracking model was then coupled to this hydrodynamic forcing to simulate the drift pathways of the bodies under the combined influence of tidal currents and the wind-driven transport.

The simulated particles exhibited oscillatory, back and forth motion driven by tides, while their overall trajectories were

influenced by shifting wind directions throughout the simulation period. Within the first week, some particles became stranded along the west coast of the Isle of Man. They were subsequently advected towards the northeast coast of Ireland, near Dublin, in early January 1918, before eventually being transported to the North Wales coast after almost 6 weeks. Overall, the model results demonstrate the capability of this type of modelling approach and show strong agreement with the observed timing of burial records for bodies recovered along the North Wales coast.

Case Study 4: Minimising Environmental Impacts from Rock Releases in Norwegian Fjords

Construction works (e.g. tunnelling) and mining operations can produce large quantities of graded rock fragments that are often disposed of within adjacent waterbodies, such as fjords. If this disposal is not carefully controlled, the potential release of large quantities of fine sediments can impact adversely on wider aquatic ecosystems and habitats (e.g. wild fish migration and spawning), and have a detrimental impact on adjacent

aquaculture operations. An experimental programme was conducted at the University of Dundee to improve current rock mass release protocols through enhanced physical understanding of the dynamic behaviour of graded rock fragment masses within fully enclosed fall-pipes and their release at depth within the affected waterbody. The videos below show an example experimental run of a simulated rock mass input within, and release beneath, a vertical fall-pipe. These videos were analysed to understand how the size-dependent settling and deposition of the rock masses affects the potential for wider dispersal of fine sediments (red particles in videos) following their release from the pipe exit.

The project was funded by Statens vegvesen (Norwegian Public Roads Administration), as an R&D project associated with the construction of the new E16 Arna-Stanghelle joint road and railway tunnel, currently under construction along the southeast shore of Sørfjorden in Norway ([Arna-Stanghelle joint project | Statens vegvesen](#)). The main results and conclusions from the experimental study into rock mass releases in vertical fall-pipes are presented in [Neshamar et al. \(2026\)](#).

4. Creating a model

What is a mathematical numerical model made of?

A hydrodynamic model provides an idealised representation of a marine system and can be understood as a set of building blocks, each representing a specific physical process or feature, applied either across the whole model domain or at defined locations. Here we demonstrate the steps involved in creating an FVCOM hydrodynamic model of the west coast of Scotland.

The model becomes specific to this region with the model configuration. Configuring the model involves providing each building block with the appropriate data and parameters, and assembling them to represent the real-world location and environmental conditions.

In the following section, each building block is introduced first through a simple illustrative example, followed by a more detailed real-world example.

The model's source code

The model's source code is the heart of a hydrodynamic model. It ensures that all parts of the model communicate and work together and behave in a way that reflects real ocean conditions.

Different models use different mathematical approaches to simulate how water moves. For example, some models (like [FVCOM](#) and [Suntans](#)) use flexible triangular grids that follow the shape of the coastline, while others (like [ROMS](#)) use more regular grid shapes.

The source code also includes rules and parameters that represent natural processes like mixing, waves, allowing the model to mimic real-world behaviour.

This figure shows the domain of a model of the west coast of Scotland - WeStCOMS. Some building blocks are applied across the whole domain (1-4 and 7), while others, such as fresh water inputs, only apply in specific locations at the coastline.

The horizontal mesh

The first step in building a hydrodynamic model is designing a numerical grid, or mesh. This grid breaks the ocean or coastal area into many small cells—like a digital puzzle—where water movement is calculated. The simplest type is a structured grid, which uses regularly spaced, block-shaped cells and works well for simple coastlines.

Loch Etive unstructured grid

Vertical mesh

The bathymetry

Bathymetry provides the essential lower boundary condition for hydrodynamic models, defining the depth of the water column across the spatial domain and shaping key features such as ocean basins, continental shelves, estuaries, and other underwater topographies.

Loch Etive bathymetry

Vertical layers

Many 3D models take the approach of stacking a 2D model mesh vertically to create the 3rd dimension. Here we choose to use a structured grid using rectangular cells to provide a simple example of 3D grid.

Environmental forcing

- Tidal forcing: The oscillating rise and fall of sea level is caused by the gravitational pull of the Moon and Sun.
- Open boundary forcing: Salinity, temperature, and currents are specified at the model edges to represent exchanges with the surrounding ocean.
- Surface forcing: Atmospheric heat fluxes warm or cool the ocean surface, while wind stress drives surface currents and promotes vertical mixing.
- Freshwater forcing: River inputs lower salinity (fresher) water and can create density-driven circulation patterns.

Tidal surface elevation amplitude (in meters) for major semidiurnal constituents M2 (left plot) and S2 (right plot) and the reference pressure gauge sites (circles)

Tidal forcing

Tides at the open boundaries of the model area are usually set using water-level data from larger global ocean models. A widely used tool for this is the [OSU Tidal Inversion software](#).

Tides are made up of several repeating waves called *tidal constituents*. The two most important are caused by the Moon (M2, about 12.4-hour cycle) and the Sun (S2, 12-hour cycle). The maps shown illustrate how these two tidal waves spatially vary around the west coast of Scotland. The white lines show the timing of the tide as it moves along the coast (co-tidal lines) and the points where these lines meet are locations where the tide has almost no height change (amphidromic points).

Sea ice
NUMERICAL MODEL

Learn more

July 2012

1993 1994 1995 1996 1997 1998 1999 2000 2001 2002 2003 2004 2005 2006 2007 2008 2009 2010

CREDITS

Open boundary forcing

Tides are a key boundary condition for coastal models, but additional open-boundary information is also needed. At the edges of the model domain, this “lateral boundary forcing” ensures that water, heat, and momentum move in and out realistically, helping maintain balance in the system.

Along with tidal elevation, the most important inputs are temperature, salinity, and non-tidal currents, which represent large-scale ocean inflows and outflows. These time-series are typically taken from a larger, lower-resolution “parent” model covering a wider area, such as a regional or global ocean model.

Click through the interactive map shown on the right hand side to see the modelled temperature hosted by the [Copernicus Marine Service](#).

The meteorological plots above show two WRF model domains—18 km (outer domain) and 2 km (inner domain)—used to provide atmospheric forcing for the WeStCOMS coastal model.

Atmospheric forcing

The sea surface is the boundary where the sea meets the atmosphere, and many important processes occur at this interface. Wind blowing across the water transfers momentum, driving currents and mixing. Heat exchange between the air and ocean warms or cools the surface. Rain adds freshwater, while evaporation removes it, and changes in atmospheric pressure can raise or lower sea level.

These surface conditions - known as **atmospheric forcing** - are usually taken from large-scale weather and climate models, such as those produced by the UK Met Office.

For regional ocean models with grid sizes of a few kilometres, global or large-scale products such as [NCEP NCAR GFS](#) (0.25° resolution) or reanalysis datasets like [ECMWF-50](#), ERA-5 are typically sufficient. However, high-resolution coastal models often require much finer atmospheric data to capture local wind patterns and coastal weather effects. In those cases, regional

weather model such as [WRF](#), run at 1-2 km resolution, are commonly used.

8a. River catchment boundaries for Loch Eive and rivers discharge from rain over catchments from WRF rainfall for each river

8b. Animation of freshwater plume behaviour in Ardmucknish Bay at the entrance to Loch Eive, illustrating changes in the fresher (lighter-coloured) surface water plume under varying tides, winds and river discharge.

River forcing

River flow data is essential for accurately predicting coastal circulation, especially when salinity-driven (baroclinic) forces dominate. During periods of strong freshwater input, river discharge can strongly influence surface currents and stratification. Climatological river datasets (e.g., [Grid 2 Grid](#)) are sometimes insufficient, as rainfall and river flow can vary dramatically from year to year - by roughly 25% to 175% of the long-term monthly average in Scotland ([CEH](#) reports in Scotland). Using realistic, time-varying river flow data greatly improves model performance.

5. Coupled models

How to represent more processes or features?

Often what we're interested in is not just physical processes...

To represent additional processes in the ocean, such as biogeochemistry, water quality, or transport of pollutants or marine life, additional models can be used.

These can be **"coupled"** with the physical circulation model, allowing them to use information for example about the ocean circulation or temperature.

In the real world, the ocean ecosystem is very complex, with processes happening and interacting on a wide range of spatial and temporal scales. However, we can never include everything in our models. Instead, we need to decide which processes are most crucial for answering the problem in question.

Applications & Complexity

The choice of which additional processes or models to use can often depend on two decisions:

1. What is the process or application required for the problem or question of interest?
2. How realistic or complex do you want (or need) your model to be?

Adding additional processes into the model may make it more similar to the real world. However, added complexity is likely to make a model more computationally expensive. So, when designing a model, a compromise is often needed, when deciding which processes are required to understand the problem of interest, alongside how fast a model needs to run (and computational power available).

This section provides some examples of different models that can be used and their applications in the marine environment.

Examples of additional models:

Biogeochemistry or water quality

- The growth of plankton and algae, or other lifeforms in the ocean, is known to be dependent on both the supply of nutrients and the physical conditions of the ocean.
- Additional models can be used to represent such processes within the ocean.
- Biogeochemical models are often used to understand “productivity” within the ocean, and are crucial for understanding the ocean’s role in carbon uptake, as part of the wider climate system.
- Water quality models can be used to focus on the growth, transport, or decay of materials that may be harmful to human health as well as the marine ecosystem.

Sediment or suspended particulates

- The transport and erosion of sediment along our coastlines is dependent on the impact of waves, tides, and ocean

circulation, as well as river sources.

- Models can be used to understand how sediment transport may evolve both in the short term as well as over 100s of years, to help plan coastal development.
- Erosion of the seabed and transport of suspended matter in the wider ocean is also affected by ocean circulation.
- Understanding the transport and settling of suspended matter is important for understanding light levels for marine life, as well as storage of carbon in the ocean.

Waves

- Wave models are needed to understand the sea-state, including the height, frequency, and direction of surface waves in the ocean.
- These can be used to support safety at sea, coastal resilience (e.g., erosion and inundation), and broader understanding of ocean processes.
- Waves will be impacted by local weather conditions and ocean currents, but swell can also have a significant impact, and will

be influenced by conditions further away.

- Waves themselves also affect surface currents in the ocean.
- Two-way coupling between ocean and wave models, where they can share information and respond to different processes, can then be used to improve ocean forecasts.

Particle tracking

- Particle tracking models allow you to follow the pathway of an individual particle, from source to end destination, like a virtual drifter in your ocean model.
- Each particle can either be simply transported by ocean currents, or can have “behaviour” assigned that responds to the local conditions along its path.
- Aside from helping our understanding of ocean circulation, these models can also have many different applications, tailored to the species or material of interest.
- For example, simulating the transport and growth of eggs or larvae of marine species, or the transport of pollutants released into the ocean.

Atmosphere and land-surface

- Ocean models are dependent on surface forcing from atmospheric conditions (e.g., wind and solar heating), as well as freshwater surfaces from river outflows.
- To improve representation of these processes, atmospheric models can be used to simulate the local weather conditions in the region of interest.
- Two-way coupling can also allow the atmosphere to respond to ocean conditions. Atmosphere-ocean interactions can influence local weather condition and are also crucial for long-term climate projections.
- Where observations of river outflows are limited, land-surface models can be very useful to represent runoff of freshwater, as well as any nutrients or contaminants along the coastline, responding to local rainfall as well as land use.

Advantages	Disadvantages
Physical process-based insight into flow phenomena and/or transport processes not readily achievable through theoretical or numerical modelling alone <i>Example: wave shoaling/breaking on an erodible beach</i>	Scale effects in downscaled models (see Scaling and Dimensional Analysis). <i>Example: need for vertical scale distortion in study of stratified flows.</i>
Direct qualitative observations on physical processes and provision of quantitative data <i>Example: turbulent mixing in stratified flows</i>	Not possible to simulate all relevant variables in correct relationships with each other - simplification or idealisation often required. <i>Example: simplified representations of vegetation or sediments in experiments</i>
Ability to measure complex phenomena beyond full theoretical understanding or current numerical modelling capabilities <i>Example: bio-stabilisation of sediments, capture of microplastics in biofilms</i>	Physical model boundaries and unrealistic forcing conditions can influence the process being simulated <i>Example: idealised wave and current conditions generated in flumes, lower flow Reynolds numbers than occur in nature.</i>
Controlled environment where individual parameters can be changed systematically when compared to field measurements <i>Example: wave-structure-seabed interactions around monopiles, breakwaters</i>	Facilities vary widely and are expensive to install and maintain. The correct facility for the application may not be available.
Direct integration of physical processes without simplifying assumptions required for analytical or numerical models <i>Example: evolution of estuarine morphodynamics based on sedimentation and erosion of mixed (sand-mud) sediments</i>	
Provision of important validation data sets for numerical models <i>Example: measurement of settling & deposition of particulate wastes from aquaculture</i>	

6. Physical modelling

Introduction

Physical models are normally used to investigate hydrodynamics and associated processes (e.g. sediment transport, pollution dispersal, etc.) for specific coastal regions or marine infrastructure (e.g. ports, harbours, breakwaters, offshore renewable energy installations and aquaculture). Laboratory experimentation may also be used to study individual hydrodynamic processes associated with characterising flow turbulence and mixing, sediment transport dynamics, stratification & buoyancy driven flows, wave dynamics and flow-ecology interactions.

See the table to the right for the advantages and disadvantages of physical modelling:

Scaling and Dimensional Analysis

In order for physical models and laboratory-based experimentation to be relevant to full-scale “*prototype*” coastal and marine problems, they have to be scaled appropriately based on achieving **similarity** between *model* and *prototype* scales:

Geometric similarity ensures model dimensions (lengths, areas and volumes) are consistent with prototype characteristic dimensions (lengths, areas and volumes).

Kinematic similarity ensures all time-dependent model properties (e.g. velocities) are scaled appropriately with equivalent prototype properties.

Dynamic similarity ensures all model forces are scaled appropriately with equivalent prototype forces.

Note: other relevant model parameters, such as time, acceleration, flow rate, pressure, etc., are obtained by combining

different geometric (length), kinematic (velocity), and dynamic (force) scale factors.

In general, many physical models often assume that the scaling of inertial and gravity forces match, resulting in **Froude number similarity** between model and prototype scales, where Froude number

$$Fr = \frac{u}{\sqrt{gL}}$$

(with u and L being characteristic velocity and lengths, respectively, and g being gravitational acceleration).

Another common modelling approach is to assume viscous forces will be important, leading to **Reynolds number similarity**, where Reynolds number

$$Re = \frac{uL}{\nu}$$

(with ν being the kinematic viscosity of the fluid).

For physical models that use the same fluid type (e.g. seawater) as the prototype scale problem they are representing, it is impossible to satisfy Froude number and Reynolds number similarity simultaneously. Hence, if Froude number similarity is sought (i.e. where gravity force is dominant) then other forces, such as viscosity or surface tension effects, are subject to so-called **scale effects**, which are often assumed negligible (e.g. when fully-turbulent flow conditions are being modelled). These other forces may, however, become important for smaller scale physical processes under investigation (see below).

Physical & biological/ecological processes		Typical prototype scale	Typical model scale
<i>Bio-stabilisation of sediments; flow turbulence; fluid-sediment interactions; microplastic capture/retention in microbial biofilms.</i>		$\mu\text{m} \rightarrow \text{mm}$	$\mu\text{m} \rightarrow \text{mm}$
<i>Sediment transport dynamics and seabed response (bedforms); flow interactions with vegetation</i>		$\text{mm} \rightarrow 10\text{s m}$	$\text{mm} \rightarrow 10\text{s m}$
<i>Current-wave-structure interactions (e.g. offshore renewables, ports, harbours, breakwaters; nature-based coastal defences)</i>		$10\text{s} \rightarrow 100\text{s m}$	$\text{m} \rightarrow 10\text{s m}$
<i>Regional estuarine and coastal hydrodynamics and morphodynamics; sea straits</i>		$100\text{s m} \rightarrow 10\text{s km}$	$\text{m} \rightarrow 10\text{s m}$
<i>Large scale oceanic flows and circulations; submarine landslides and turbidity currents</i>		$10\text{s} \rightarrow 1000\text{s km}$	$\text{m} \rightarrow 10\text{s m}$

Scales of problems under investigation

Physical modelling and laboratory experimentation can help us understand a wide range of physical and biological/ecological processes in coastal and marine aquatic environments over a range of scales from $\mu\text{m} \rightarrow 1000\text{s km}$.

7. Laboratory Facilities

Wave (and current) flumes

These normally consist of rectangular open channels with a wave maker at one end to generate uni-directional waves. In some cases, recirculating pumps are also present to generate colinear currents. These facilities are typically used to understand wave (and current) interactions with natural coastal features (e.g. beaches), marine vegetation, and/or coastal and marine infrastructure.

Example applications: renewable energy (wind, wave, tidal) - wave-current-structure interactions; ship design; oil & gas; wave interactions with vegetation; beach swash dynamics; sediment transport dynamics under waves

Wave flume facilities in MASTS institutes:

- [Kelvin Hydrodynamics Laboratory](#) (University of Strathclyde)

- [University of Aberdeen Random Wave Flume \(AURWF\)](#)
- [Surface Wave \(and Current\) Flume \(University of Dundee\)](#)

Wave Tank (Kelvin Hydrodynamics Laboratory)

Wave (and current) basins

These are large water tanks with multiple wave makers to generate wave fields in two horizontal dimensions. Recirculating pumps may also generate colinear, perpendicular or oblique

currents to wave direction. These facilities are typically used to understand multi-directional wave (and current) interactions with coastal and marine infrastructure.

Example applications: renewable energy (wind, wave, tidal) – wave-current-structure interactions; ship design; oil & gas installations; generation of rogue & extreme waves

Wave basin facilities at MASTS institutes:

- [FloWave Ocean Energy Research Facility](#) (University of Edinburgh)
- [Wave Basin](#) (Heriot Watt University)

Recirculating current channels and flumes

These facilities are normally straight, rectangular channels with recirculating pumps that generate uni-directional steady or unsteady open channel flow conditions. The channel may be inclined at angle to simulate bed slopes. These facilities may recirculate water or both water and sediments and are typically

used to investigate river flow and sediment transport processes, including impacts on in-channel infrastructure.

Example applications: Open channel flow hydrodynamics and flow turbulence, sediment transport dynamics and morphodynamics, bed scour at structures (e.g. bridge piers, monopiles), longitudinal dispersion, vegetated flows, bio-colonisation of sediment beds, biofilm development, testing of model tidal turbines.

Recirculating flume facilities at MASTS institutes:

- [Aberdeen Open Channel Facility \(AOCF\)](#) (University of Aberdeen)
- [Large recirculating tank facility](#) (University of Dundee)
- [Tilting flume facilities](#) (Heriot-Watt University)

Oscillatory water tunnels

These facilities are bespoke, closed horizontal duct channels to study processes near or within the wave boundary layer at

realistic near-prototype scales. Horizontal flow is driven by pistons at both ends of the closed channel that generate symmetrical or non-symmetrical oscillatory forcing of enclosed water volume.

Example applications: sediment transport dynamics and morphodynamic evolution under oscillatory flows; flow-sediment-seabed infrastructure interactions (e.g. bed scour, dynamic loading); flow interactions with vegetation.

Oscillatory flow tunnel facilities at MASTS institutes:

- [Aberdeen Oscillatory Flow Tunnel](#) (AOFT) (University of Aberdeen)

Stratified Flow Facilities

These are bespoke saltwater-freshwater facilities that simulate estuarine and tidal inlet hydrodynamics, and can be adapted to simulate other continental slope processes such as density-driven gravity and turbidity currents. Within the estuarine/tidal inlet

configuration, tidal forcing can be introduced by saltwater volume displacement within the facility, generating a saltwater tidal intrusion along a model estuarine channel. Freshwater forcing can also be introduced via a recirculating pump to represent river flow along the channel opposing the saltwater intrusion.

Example applications: estuarine and fjordic hydrodynamics; fresh-salt water exchange flows in coastal areas; effects of man-made tidal barrages/barriers and/or natural topographic obstructions (e.g. sills, sandbars); submarine gravity and turbidity currents (dense water and sediment mass flows);

Stratified Flow Facilities at MASTS institutes:

- [Channel-basin Facility](#) and [Large Recirculating Tank Facility](#) (University of Dundee)

Flow visualisation measurement techniques

Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) uses laser sheet illumination of seeded flows for high-resolution measurement of flow velocity fields; spatial and temporal variations in mean flow properties and turbulence characteristics.

Particle Tracking Velocimetry (PTV) is an optical based measurement technique for tracking individual particles or clusters of particles within a flow field. It is useful for tracking tagged sediment particles within an open channel or oscillatory boundary flow, or the sedimentation of colour-coded particles within granular flows or sediment-laden plumes.

Laser/Light Induced Fluorescence (LIF) is a measurement technique for passive tracer (e.g. fluorescent dye) concentrations through illumination within a laser/light sheet. This can be used to measure ambient fluid entrainment and dilution of turbulent jets and plumes in the marine environment (e.g. marine wastewater discharges, pollution spills, black smokers).

Point and Profile Measurement Techniques

Laser Doppler Anemometry (LDA) provides high-resolution point measurements of mean flow velocity and turbulence characteristics (for clear seeded flow only). This technique can be particularly useful in confined spaces (e.g. within vegetation patches) where other flow visualisation methods (PIV/PTV) are not possible.

Acoustic/ultrasonic velocity profilers (ADV/UVP) provide point or profile measurements of flow velocity and turbulence characteristics. Measurements possible in both clear (seeded) or turbid (sediment-laden) flows.

Micro-conductivity probes provide high-resolution profile measurements of density structure and mixing characteristics within stratified flows (e.g. characterising the interaction between fresh and saline water masses estuarine and coastal marine environments).

8. Scottish Models

The Scottish Shelf Model

The Scottish Shelf Model is a suite of hydrodynamic models focused on Scottish shelf waters. This wider domain covers UK waters with the Scottish coastline at high resolution. The development of the models was led by the Marine Directorate of the Scottish Government and the National Oceanography Centre (NOC) develop the wider domain model. This model has a wide variety of marine science applications including tidal stream resource and impact assessments, aquaculture such as sea lice connectivity and risk assessment. This 3D model is an implementation of the [Finite Volume Community Ocean Model \(FVCOM\)](#), which utilises an unstructured horizontal mesh, and horizontal resolution at the coastline of around 500 - 1000 m.

More information, including available model runs, is available at marine.gov.scot. The model output is open source with a [modelled climatology available on request](#), and the latest reanalysis data from the [Scottish Shelf Waters Reanalysis Service](#).

Wider Loch Linnhe System (WLLS)

The Wider Loch Linnhe System model has a domain covering many of the Inner Hebrides from the southern tip of the Mull of Kintyre to the Isle of Skye in the north. This 3D model was created primarily for aquaculture applications, as there are many salmon farms within Loch Linnhe, in order to help decision makers understand the potential environmental impact of aquaculture in this region. The horizontal mesh has a variable resolution from 5 km at the open boundary to approximately 15 m within some regions of Loch Linnhe.

East Coast of Lewis and Harris (ECLH)

The East Coast of Lewis and Harris model covers the Minch and Skye region, although the east coast of the outer Hebrides are most highly resolved. This 3D model was created to help understand the potential environmental impact of aquaculture developments along the east coast of the outer Hebrides and to investigate the potential sea lice connectivity between aquaculture developments. The horizontal mesh has a variable resolution from 3 km at the open boundary and more typically 100 - 200 m in highly resolved areas.

The model is part of the Scottish Shelf Model suite of hydrodynamic models and more information, including available model runs, is available at marine.gov.scot. The model output is open source and [available on request](#).

The Pentland Firth and Orkney Waters (PFOW)

The Orkney Islands have a network of channel with fast tidal currents, and the Pentland Firth experiences the fastest tidal currents in Scotland. This is therefore a region with significant tidal stream resource and is home to the European Marine Energy Centre (EMEC). This 3D model was created for tidal stream resource and environmental impact assessment, but also for aquaculture applications such as sea lice connectivity. The horizontal mesh has a variable resolution from 5 km at the open boundary to 100 - 150 m within the Pentland Firth.

The model is part of the Scottish Shelf Model suite of hydrodynamic models and more information, including available model runs, is available at marine.gov.scot. The model output is open source and [available on request](#).

Firth of Clyde

The Firth of Clyde model has a domain covering the Clyde Firth and the North Channel between Scotland and Northern Ireland. The domain extends as far as Isle of Tiree and the Isle of Coll to the North and the Isle of Man to the South. This region is important for a wide range of social and economic reasons including aquaculture, fishing and tourism, and there is also a high population density along much of the Clyde in Glasgow with pollution being an issue. This 3D model was primarily developed to understand the potential environmental impacts of aquaculture but has been used for many environmental applications by SEPA. The horizontal mesh has a variable resolution from 3 km at the open boundary to a more typical resolution of 200 - 300 m within the inner Firth of Clyde.

The model is part of the Scottish Shelf Model suite of hydrodynamic models and more information, including available model runs, is available at marine.gov.scot. The model output is open source and [available on request](#).

Shetland

The Shetland model is an implementation of the Finite Volume Community Ocean Model (FVCOM) and has a domain covering the northern isles of Shetland and Orkney, although Orkney is nowhere near as well resolved as Shetland. The horizontal model grid is unstructured with the highest horizontal resolution around Shetland of approximately 30 m. This 3D model is being further developed by the National Oceanography Centre (NOC) on behalf of the Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA) and the Scottish Government Marine Directorate and will primarily be used for aquaculture environmental assessment applications.

The model is part of the Scottish Shelf Model suite of hydrodynamic models and more information, including available model runs, is available from marine.gov.scot and the [Marine Directorate Oceanography Group](#).

Firth of Forth and Tay Estuary

The Firth of Forth and Tay Estuary model has been developed by the Scottish Government Marine Directorate Oceanography Group for a variety of marine science applications. Most recently it has been used to model offshore wind farms off the Scottish east coast to understand their potential impacts on marine physical processes including water column stratification. This 3D model is an implementation of FVCOM and a few different unstructured grid versions have been developed resolving different areas from the coastline to the offshore wind farms.

The model is part of the Scottish Shelf Model suite of hydrodynamic models and more information, including available model runs, is available from marine.gov.scot and the [Marine Directorate Oceanography Group](#).

Moray Firth

The Moray Firth is the largest firth in Scotland and is regularly visited by marine wildlife and the area includes a special area of conservation (SAC), proposed Marine Protected Area (MPA) and several Special Protection Areas (SPA). In addition, the Moray Firth is a host of multiple wind farm sites, specifically in the Smith Bank area. This 3D model is an implementation of [FVCOM](#) and has a domain covering the Cromarty Firth, the Dornoch Firth, the Moray coast as well as the coast from Fraserburgh to Aberdeen. The model grid is unstructured with the highest horizontal resolution in the Cromarty and Dornoch Firth as well as the Smith Bank area. The node spacing varies from less than 50 m to approximately 3 km along part of the outer boundary however in the finer resolution areas the resolution is typically around 100 - 200 m. The vertical water column is resolved using 10 terrain following sigma layers, each representing 10 % of the water column.

WeStCOMS

The West Coast of Scotland Coastal Ocean Modelling System (WeStCOMS) is an operational forecasting implementation FVCOM coupled with the high-resolution regional atmospheric model ([WRF](#)). The Scottish Association for Marine Science ([SAMS](#)) physical oceanographic group led by [Dr Dmitry Aleynik](#) has developed WeStCOMS. WeStCOMS modelling system produces an estimate of the ocean physical parameters over the nearest past and five day forecasts. The parameters modelled are ocean temperature and salinity, sea level, ocean currents and diffusivity. Smaller nested sub-domains with higher horizontal resolution varying from 32 m to 500 m include the Loch Etive, Loch Ewe, area around the Isle of Rum and near Loch Melfort. Both the atmospheric and ocean models output data are freely available via the SAMS [THREDDS](#) server.

The Finite Volume Community Ocean Model ([FVCOM](#)) is a prognostic, unstructured-grid, finite-volume, free-surface, 3-D

primitive equation coastal ocean circulation model developed by joint efforts at UMASSD-WHOI.

9. Conclusions

There are many different types of marine and ocean models, from physical models in laboratory tanks to numerical models that solve complex differential equations representing the main physical processes. Models will never fully represent reality as it is hard to include all real-life conditions or to resolve all the relevant processes. However, simplifying reality can often be a useful way to understand the main processes at play. Physical models are generally a powerful way to explore small-scale and highly complex processes such as how waves and currents affect the movement of marine sediments. In contrast, numerical ocean models are useful to explore and predict the larger-scale structure and movement of our oceans and coastal waters. Models can provide a picture of the ocean everywhere, and for any time you want. They allow us to consider different scenarios, including either future climate or development of marine

infrastructure. However, they will always be simplifications of reality. Therefore, observations of the ocean are still crucial for providing input into our models as well as validating their outputs.

This story map has provided a brief introduction to the world of numerical and physical ocean modelling from the perspective of a few coastal modelling scientists within the MASTS community. We hope you have found it useful to understand more of the capabilities of different models and potential for using model data in your own marine science applications.

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**How to view this Story
Map**

This Story Map was designed to be viewed on a large computer screen in Google Chrome. If possible, please try to view it on a computer, laptop or iPad. If you are viewing via another platform please be aware the Story Map may not display properly.

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